

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 7.1

Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications Plan

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Deliverable 7.1

Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications Plan

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
D	Dissemination
C	Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
AI	Artificial Intelligence
HRM	Human Resources Management
NLP	Natural Language Processing
CBR	Case-Based Reasoning
HR	Human Resources
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UN	United Nations
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
USP	Unique Selling Proposition
IF	Impact Factor

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1 Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a detailed overview on the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy that will be implemented during the BIAS project. This strategy is integrated under WP7: Communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

As WP7 leader, LOBA will be responsible for the overall management and support of activities defined under the present dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan, including monitoring the performance, and develop the main dissemination and communication channels, tools, and materials to be used during the project. In collaboration with Task 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5, led by Crowdhelix, the present plan will also address the networking and clustering, as well as the project and community sustainability strategy, aiming to ensure timely promotion of project's outcomes and engagement of parties outside the Consortium, interested to use or adopt them.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communications plan outlines a detailed planning of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in a systematic manner, with the aim of performing actions and campaigns that reach specific groups and audiences for specific purposes. For its part, the first version of the project and community sustainability plan included in this document, provides the main activities to ensure sustainability after the project ends.

All partners will be actively involved in the dissemination, exploitation and communication actions implementation, and their involvement will contribute to a satisfactory dissemination of the project's objectives, activities, and results. In general, the expected contribution from partners is to:

- Implement publicity and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European and international levels.
- Exploit their contacts and networks.
- Supply news and updates for the web portal and newsletter.
- Help to keep the project's Social Media Accounts alive and active.
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes.
- Contribute with scientific papers acknowledging the BIAS project.
- Define their own project and community sustainability strategy.

2 Introduction

This deliverable provides detailed information about the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials, and tools used to support an effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the project. Further updates of this document will be provided in the periodic reports and on M24 under D7.2.

This deliverable is divided into 10 main sections:

- **Section 1** – “Executive Summary”: describes these deliverable objectives and what is expected from the consortium partners.
- **Section 2** – “Introduction”: it lists the deliverable’s sections.
- **Section 3** – “BIAS in a nutshell”: it describes the project’s mission and objectives.
- **Section 4** - “The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communications Plan”: describes in which phases the DEC will be divided into and its main objectives.
- **Section 5** - “Strategy”: timeline to implement the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities. In turn, it will be divided into several subtopics:
 - Identity: presenting the BIAS branding.
 - Target groups: description of each BIAS target audience, mapping of actors (at local, national, and European level) by each partner and engagement strategies for each target audience.
 - BIAS partners’ support in the project’s dissemination and communication: how the partners will contribute to the D&C.
 - Channels and tools: detailed description of the means that will be utilised and the processes that will be followed during the implementation of the project to achieve its maximum impact.
 - Networking and clustering: identify and establish a link to other existing EU-funded projects.
 - Trustworthy AI Helix: creation and management process of the BIAS Helix, as well as the events related to it.
 - Project and community sustainability: definition of the main activities that will ensure the project’s sustainability.
- **Section 6** - “Internal communication”: procedures created to communicate internally, with a special focus on the reporting procedures.
- **Section 7** - “Evaluation Criteria (KPI’s)”: a description of the desirable goals and KPIs of the dissemination and communication plan, as well as the reporting procedure adopted.
- **Section 8** - “Schedule & Timing”: timeline for the launching of the main materials and tools for BIAS DEC strategy.
- **Section 9** – “Conclusion”: main conclusion from this deliverable.
- **Section 10** – “Annexes”: the deliverables annexes.

3 BIAS in a nutshell

BIAS is a four-year project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme, that will empower the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Human Resources Management (HRM) community by addressing algorithmic biases and mitigating them.

Because AI is increasingly deployed in the labour market to recruit, train, and engage employees or monitor for infractions that can lead to disciplinary proceedings, the BIAS project will investigate its use in the labour market. The project will also study how human and societal biases are potentially reproduced in AI-based systems and develop tools to identify and mitigate these biases. BIAS will do this through a 3-pronged empirical research methodology and an impact strategy:

- **The research strategy will involve:**
 - The creation in each country of national labs (communities of practitioners, employees, HRM, and AI specialists with a special focus on marginalised people/communities that will be involved in the co-creation and all other engagement activities of BIAS), a needs analysis, stakeholder involvement (by resorting to surveys and interviews to AI developers and HR [Human Resources] executives) and co-creation workshops.
 - The creation of a proof-of-concept for innovative technology based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) for use in an HR recruitment use case. The system will contain two modules: one for bias detection and another for bias mitigation.
 - An ethnographic fieldwork, with employers, employees, and AI developers from different European countries providing richly textured information about current experiences and future imaginaries of bias and AI in employment settings to PhDs and researchers.
- **The impact strategy will involve:**
 - Capacity building sessions.
 - Awareness-raising events.
 - Networking and clustering both online and in physical events.
 - Open access scientific publications.
 - Launch of open-source code.
 - A viable commercialisation strategy (including a market analysis and commercialisation roadmap; and initial explorations of regulatory acceptability).

BIAS is composed of 9 leading partners (from 9 different countries) in the areas of i) AI solutions, ii) SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) knowledge, iii) diversity, iv) dissemination and communication, v) gender equality in HR practices and vi) industrial uptake and commercialization. In total, the consortium is made up of 4 universities, 3 communication partners, 1 large industrial organisation and 1 SME. One partner, Bern University of Applied Sciences, is an Associated Partner.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Develop trustworthy, novel tools for bias identification and bias mitigation in AI/NLP systems that can be deployed across multiple applications.

- Engage in robust stakeholder engagement and co-creation, especially targeting marginalised people/communities, for the creation of the Debiaser in the specific use case of recruitment.
- Empower the AI and HRM community through capacity building to develop better technology and institute better practices by integrating concerns about bias into their everyday workflow and strategic considerations. Raise awareness among specialists and the public about the importance of addressing algorithmic bias.
- Gain a richly detailed understanding of bias in recruitment and HRM, especially as it relates to the use of AI and technology, that advances the field of worker studies as well as making capacity building activities more relevant and informing future trajectories of NLP and AI research.
- Make hiring practices less biased through the development of a proof-of-concept system that can be further developed into a commercially viable product to reduce bias in AI systems used in recruitment.

BIAS will focus on four priorities, with which the project is highly aligned by its overarching strategy of the work programme:

- Digital Agenda.
- Artificial Intelligence.
- Co-programmed European Partnerships.
- Social sciences and humanities.

4 The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communications Plan

The dissemination, exploitation, and communications (DEC) strategy has been devised with one main goal in mind: achieving the greatest possible impact within the allocated budget envelope, amongst the target groups identified.

The plan will comprise the following stages:

- **Stage 0 – Knowledge:** The importance of situational analysis of the project will determine the definition of a coherent, consistent campaign strategically aligned with BIAS’ DNA and the personification of the project.
- **Stage 1 – BIAS’ Strategy:** The brand strategy phase includes the creation at a holistic dimension of the project entire brand. For this, it is necessary to find, based on the goals and analysis performed in the previous stage, the answers and content for the central elements that will be the founders of all experiences and actions to be generated by the brand: values, attributes (how we want the brand to be perceived), positioning and brand language.
- **Stage 2 – Action Plan:** The Action Plan includes the detailed planning of all communication activities for Stage 1 and Stage 2 of the BIAS campaign in a systematic manner. This involves:
 - Creation of actions: creative definition of the communication action as well as the briefing of how this will be put into practice.
 - Definition of objectives: contextualization of the action in terms of how each action/message will be adapted to suit any target audience.
 - Definition of and assignment to the responsible party to carry out each action.
 - Timing: definition of the period of the action based on prior coordination with the other WPs.
 - Materials: definition of the communication materials to be created.

The main objectives of this DEC Plan are to:

- Raise awareness of the project’s activities and events.
- Communicate and disseminate the results of the project among the main targets groups.
- Make use of a variety of channels to efficiently communicate the project amongst the main target groups.
- Develop printed support materials (such as poster, roll-ups, stationary, etc.) and digital materials (videos, infographics, etc.) when necessary.
- Ensure regular communication to keep the target groups, the media and other projects/initiatives updated on the project, through emailing, press releases and newsletters.
- Create and manage a clustering helix called the “Trustworthy AI helix” on Crowdhelix’s platform, managing the helix’s events.
- Create a link to other existing projects and initiatives related to BIAS mission.
- Foster the clustering with BIAS sister projects.
- Ensure the community and sustainability of the project beyond its duration.

5 Strategy

For the DEC of the expected results, we have selected the most effective channels of communication, materials, and tools to maximise the project dissemination, increase awareness about objectives, activities and results and contribute to the engagement of target groups and stakeholders to ensure a successful implementation of activities with a measurable impact. LOBA will define guidelines for a high impact dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy in collaboration with CHX and the consortium, following four main stages:

1. **Online presence and brand identity (M1-M6):** social media channels, project website, brand identity and project stationary are created.
2. **Early results and engagement (M6-M12):** early promotion of the project on the website (and social media channels) through tools such as newsletters, promotional video, teaser video, press release; and running of first follower campaigns.
3. **Target groups loyalty building and monitoring (M12-M48):** production and promotion of a comprehensive set of tools (supports and channels) to disseminate key messages extracted from BIAS' results to stakeholders in a way that encourages them to relate to the project.
4. **Sustainability and follow up (M3-M48):** identification of contacts, mechanism to ensure a persistent visibility of project's outcomes, production and promotion of results and tools (supports and channels).

The DEC strategy outlined in this deliverable will be reviewed and detailed by Month 24.

5.1 Identity

The identity for BIAS was developed in the first two months of the project and will be systematically used in all dissemination and communication actions and materials produced under the frame of the project, such as templates, brochures, website, posters, roll-up banners, videos, etc.

BIAS brand identity encompasses different noticeable elements (such as colours, font, logo, etc), that can instantly be associated with the project. The development of the project's brand included a thorough background analysis of the project, and assessing the brand values, attributes, positioning, and language.

During the kick-off meeting, the visual identity of the project was discussed. LOBA made sure to collect the consortium's inputs on how they envisage the project's communication and keywords like "captivating", "colourful and standing out", "original", "comprehensible and interesting to a variety of stakeholders", and "clear and immediate for all audiences" were mentioned.

Keeping this in mind, LOBA has developed a presentation of the brand to showcase the initial version to the partners. After gathering inputs from the consortium, a final version was reached (Annex 1).

With the objective of representing diversity, as the project aims to mitigate diversity biases and work towards a fair and equal labour market, we've used different shapes and different colours to represent this idea. Some shapes in the logo are more rounded, symbolising the human element of the project, and others are more sharp angles, symbolising the technological element. These sharp angles are used in the "IA" of "BIAS", taking advantage of the word play between "IA" and "AI" (Artificial Intelligence), and connecting the technological element of these shapes to the AI dimension present in the project's name. By combining shapes and colours, we create equality in diversity. These colours are purple, yellow, and green, that represent wisdom, optimism, and technology, respectively.

• logo proposal

• AI reference font
• Futuristic font

• "Softer" approach to AI
• AI as a tool, and not as the focus of the project

Figure 1: Logo proposal

The logo of the project is the following:

Figure 2: BIAS official logo

The logo is accompanied by the claim "Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market", which aims to clearly convey the mission and motivational driver of the project.

A brand manual dictating the rules and guidelines on the elements of BIAS identity and how it should be used, has also been developed (Annex 2).

The logo is available in the consortium repository in different versions and formats:

- Logo with and without claim
- Logo in black and colour, with the yellow, purple, and green dots
- Logo in ai, jpeg, png, svg formats

5.2 Target groups

- The BIAS project will follow a targeted dissemination strategy for each identified target group based on the needs and characteristics of each group. Thus, we will be able to achieve the maximum impact at every dissemination activity that will be implemented throughout the project. Table 1 below presents the different categories of target groups that BIAS has defined as the most significant ones for the dissemination and communication purposes.

Table 1: Categories of target groups, description, and examples of actors

Category	Description	BIAS actors (examples)
Key Players	Key players are directly concerned with the project, having an economic interest and power to influence and contribute to the introduction of the innovative solutions developed into global markets. They engage and collaborate easily if they see proof of the project’s advantages and economic benefits.	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyse data - LinkedIn, Indeed, itForte, Dice, Angel.co, Authentic Jobs, naukri.com
		New technologies developers
		Public and private investors
Context Setters	Context setters have the power to change structures, standards, policies, regulations, and framework conditions. Engaging with this group is key to achieve a long-term impact of the project outcomes.	Policy makers at international level - EU Agency for Fundamental Rights, UN Industrial Development Organization, European Social Fund
		Standardization organizations - CEN CENELEC
		Professional networks and platforms for both businesses and employees - European Association of People Management, International Labour Organization, Business Europe, European Trade Union Confederation
Advocates	Advocates don’t have a direct economic interest in the project outcomes, but are highly relevant in the social, educational, and academic context. Their endorsement means public support and reputation, and the build-up of social and knowledge structures.	Individual workers, such as those engaged in co-creation workshops and ethnographic interviews
		Educators, both secondary and higher education
		Citizen groups and advocacy organizations - ILGA-Europe (LGBTQ+ organization for Europe and Central Asia), European Network Against Racism, Algorithmic Justice League, Age Platform Europe
		Academics, researchers, and think tanks - Center for Intersectional Justice, Future Advocacy AI Think Tank, Global

		Partnership on Artificial Intelligence, Algorithm Watch
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5.2.1 Mapping of actors by each partner

Between Month 1 and Month 2, all consortium partners were requested to map local/national/European actors belonging to the target groups identified in the table above. This is considered the initial pool of targets (the BIAS initial community) and it can be found in the [Annex 3](#).

In this table it will be possible to see the following information:

- Name of the actor (only organisations. All identified individuals have been removed from the table and will only be accessible for internal consultation, as the content is sensitive).
- Type of target audience (key player, context setter or advocate).
- Category within the target audience (as presented in the table above).
- Country/region/city (to understand the level in which they operationalise).
- Institution/organisational affiliation.
- Project activities in which they may be involved (so we can already relate and involve them with a specific project activity or task, example: survey, national labs, co-creation workshops, etc.).
- Website link (if applicable).
- Brief description (about what they do, what is their expertise, etc. - 100 words max).
- Key words relating to their expertise within their profession (so we can better understand which expertise areas they are connected to).

For many of these organizations we have also identified individuals who we will use to make initial contact or whom we already have relationships with.

During this mapping exercise we identified a total of 126 organizations with the following breakdown. A full overview of the mapping with the most relevant information for each organization can be found in Annex 3:

Key Players

- 13 Specific platforms using AI systems to analyse data
- 25 New technologies developers
- 9 Public and private investors

Context Setters

- 5 Policymakers at international, national, and local level
- 3 Standardisation organisations
- 18 Professional networks and platforms for both businesses and employees

Advocates

- 4 Trade unions
- 13 Citizen groups and advocacy organisations
- 36 Academic organisations/think tanks

Through this mapping, we will be able to personalise our D&C. It will also help partners to know with whom they should communicate and disseminate the project.

The aim will be to contact these actors at specific times of the project, disseminating results that might interest them or inviting them to get involved in a particular activity or task of the project, according to their area of expertise.

This mapping will be updated regularly, throughout the project.

5.2.2 Engagement strategies

The involvement of stakeholders is a key element of the BIAS methodology, and as such we have defined the following objectives and associated steps to ensure a successful engagement of stakeholders.

Each of these steps are outlined below and followed by a brief description.

Identify stakeholder categories and decide on the level of granularity of stakeholder types.

An initial taxonomy of stakeholders is outlined in section “Target groups” (and presented in Table 1), based on the identification and analysis of stakeholders’ categories first identified during the development of the proposal. The actors within these categories have been identified and described in the previous section.

Identify stakeholders’ motivations and why each stakeholder type should be engaged.

For developing an efficient engagement strategy, it is important to define the reasons for reaching each type of stakeholder and identify their driver and motivations, because it allows us to tailor our discussion and messages towards the different types of stakeholders.

Identifying stakeholders’ motivations and the reasons why each stakeholder type should be engaged enables us to make sure that the topics for discussion raised by the project match stakeholders’ interests, needs and expectations.

Thus, we want to engage stakeholders in ways that are useful to them, by providing a useful service and to encourage them to continue an active engagement and involvement with BIAS.

Table 2: Stakeholders interests, pain points, added value and key messages

Key Players	
Target profile	An investor who is interested in contributing to the technology created with new AI-based solutions.
Interests and pain points	They have an economic interest and intent to influence and contribute to the introduction of the innovative solutions developed into global markets. If they see proof of the project's advantages and economic benefit, they will engage and collaborate. As investors, they always

	run the risk of betting on solutions that do not generate the expected results.
Added value	More innovative solutions will be created in this project thanks to the involvement of these Key Players.
Key message	Your help and support will be essential to create disruptive solutions that fit the global marketplace and the needs of employees and employers.
Context Setters	
Target profile	A policy maker involved in the creation of regulations and laws related to job recruitments.
Interests and pain points	They are interested in changing structures, standards, policies, regulations, and framework conditions. One possible problem is the lack of cooperation and/or transparency on the part of the entities that they engage with or that are inserted to.
Added value	Through the context setters' sphere of power, we can more easily see our technology being used in the entities' recruitment processes.
Key message	It is possible to create an artificial technology that reduces bias and that makes hiring processes more impartial. You can help us spread this idea.
Advocates	
Target profile	Advocacy organisations that are interested in creating fairer job recruitments.
Interests and pain points	They are interested in the social, educational, and academic context of the project outcomes, rather than its economic advantages. In that sense, they want fairer working conditions, which includes an unbiased job recruitment. Their main problems are the lack of support from higher authorities, as well as certain social and economic obstacles that affect them directly or indirectly.
Added value	Thanks to the inputs from the advocates, the solutions created from the workshops and ethnographic interviews will be better suited to the needs of their end users.
Key message	We're working towards equal opportunities in the labour market. With your support, we'll be able to create a technology that will minimise biases and make human resource management fairer.

Match the right means and media/channels with the type of stakeholders.

For this, we have identified different means (one-way dissemination vs. two-way communication) and media/channels (e.g., e-mails, press releases, articles in dedicated blogs, websites, conferences, workshops, advertising, social networks) through which different stakeholder types should be reached.

The project will adopt this approach to optimise project resources and ensure that communications are relevant to as many different categories of stakeholders as possible. The definition of some channels and tools is described in [Annex 4](#).

Table 3: Engagement strategies and channels and tools used for each target audience.

Target audience	Engagement strategy	Channels and tools
Key Players	Involve the key players in mapping the needs of the project and in the co-creation of AI-based solutions through the workshops that will be held. The goal will be that, through close contact they will have in mapping the problem and creating the solution, they can facilitate future use of the technology developed by the project.	Helix events, summer school on debiasing AI systems, capacity building events, closing conference, expert interviews, Bias-Free Helix, ethnographic interviews, e-learning MOOC, website, promotional materials, factsheets, social media, press releases, newsletter and mailing lists, promotional videos, scientific publications, white papers, mass media articles, external events, clustering with related projects.
Context Setters	Provide a space in which their ideas on the project topic can be shared with the audience. Involve them in the co-creation of AI-based solutions.	Physical co-creation, digital co-creation, Helix events, awareness raising events, capacity building events, regulatory acceptability workshop, closing conference, expert interviews, survey, Bias-free Helix, ethnographic interviews, e-learning MOOC, website, promotional materials, factsheets, social media, press releases, promotional videos, scientific publications, white papers, mass media articles, clustering with related projects.
Advocates	Involve advocates in two of the three phases of the project: in the co-creation of AI-based	Physical co-creation, digital co-creation, Helix events, awareness raising events,

	<p>solutions, by allowing their participation in the workshops, and in the ethnographic fieldwork, by involving people in this category in the interviews conducted. Since they are some of the main communities impacted by the results of the technology created, it is important that they are part of its construction and give their inputs regarding the BIAS experienced in recruitment processes.</p>	<p>closing conference, survey, ethnographic interviews, e-learning MOOC, website, promotional materials, factsheets, social media, press releases, promotional videos, popular media articles, external events.</p>
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Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of each of the different ways of reaching out to stakeholders and decide how cost-effectiveness is to be evaluated or measured.

Aside from the economic and time costs that need to be considered, it is also important to recognise dissemination & communication materials and channels that may be costly in terms of time and resources, since they can offer potential to attain a certain strategic objective (for example, paid campaigns on social media or the production of booths for the events).

5.3 BIAS partners’ support in the project’s dissemination and communication

All the partners have Person Months in WP7, therefore, some of the involvement and activities that partners can carry out to contribute to the dissemination of the project are the following:

- Contribute to the project’s Social Media channels to keep them active, up-to-date, and interesting, by informing the WP7 Leader about relevant content for social media such as events, achievements or interesting information that should be published in the social media channels. This will be done through a Google Form ([Annex 5](#)).
- Contribute to the project’s website and newsletter by providing to WP7 Leader with relevant news and updates.
- Implement publicity and dissemination campaigns in their own countries/regions and at European level:
 - Sharing content posted in BIAS social media.
 - Sharing translated content posted in BIAS social media.
 - Posting content about the project in their own professional or personal channels mentioning @BIASProjectEU or #BIAS (more on section 5.5.2). Conducting dissemination in their own professional or personal channels (corporate newsletter, blogs, website, etc).
- Exploit their contacts and networks, distributing newsletters, emailing or press releases in their countries/regions.

- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes, through presentations, exhibitions, distributing/displaying promotional material (i.e., brochure, goodies, roll-up, poster...).
- Contribute with scientific papers acknowledging the BIAS project.

5.3.1 Contributions already made by partners

Some partners have already made a couple of posts announcing the project kick-off meeting and goals on their organisations' social media since the beginning of the project:

- DIGI: post on [LinkedIn](#), with the following statistics:
 - Total engagements - counted from 2/12 until 8/12
 - Impressions – 29,482
 - Reactions - 31
 - Comments - 1
 - Reposts - 5
 - Video view - 792 Minutes or 13.2 hours
 - Top video viewer demographics:
 - Software developer – 8.7%
 - Salesperson – 5%
 - Recruiter – 3.4%
 - Project Manager – 2.7%
 - Human Resources Specialists – 2.4%
- BFH: post on [LinkedIn](#), with the following statistics:
 - Time Range: 02.11.-15.12.22
 - Impressions: 1'987
 - Shares: 1
 - Reactions: 27
 - Comments: 2
- Mascha Kurpicz-Briki (from BFH): post on [LinkedIn](#), with the following statistics:
 - Time Range: 02.11.22 – 15.12.22
 - Views: 5'161
 - Shares: 2
 - Reactions: 107
 - Comments: 4
- Mascha Kurpicz-Briki (from BFH): post from [Twitter](#), with the following statistics:
 - Time Range: 02.11.22 – 15.12.22
 - Views: 95
 - Engagement: 9
 - Retweet: 1
 - Likes: 4

Since the beginning of the project, BFH has already made some BIAS dissemination through its website:

- [BFH News Item - English, German, French:](#)
 - Live since: 02.11.22

- Page Views 162 / Unique Page views: 143 until 15.12.22
- [BFH Project Website - English, German, French:](#)
 - Live since: 17.11.22
 - Page views: 16 / Unique Page views: 13 until 15.12.22

5.4 Communication, dissemination, and visibility as required in the GA

According to Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, it is worth highlighting the following requirements that the project will comply during the implementation of all dissemination and communication activities.

Visibility – European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 3: EU Emblem

- The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text.
- Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.
- When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.
- For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them

the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Quality of information - Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For the Associated Partner, Bern University, according to their funding contract with the Swiss government, BIAS must add the following sentence in the publication of research results: “This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)”.

5.5 Channels and tools

To successfully put into practice the Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications plan, BIAS will make use of several channels and tools. As the dissemination and communication leader, LOBA will ensure the ongoing synergy between the project’s activities to make the most out of the content produced within the project, and by communicating the knowledge in different styles (infographics, videos, GIFs, images, etc) for different channels (website, social networks, media, events, etc). Several tools and channels will be used to support the communication of the right messages to the targeted audiences.

5.5.1 Website

BIAS website will provide information about the scope of the project, objectives, main activities, and events, and it will also give access to project’s outputs and public results. It will allow the registration for the project’s activities and promote the Trustworthy AI Helix and make a link to it. The website will be used to engage the target groups to be engaged with the project to take actions such as:

- Subscribe our newsletters.
- Register for the co-creation workshops, capacity building sessions, online raising awareness sessions and events.
- Becoming a member of the National Labs.
- Use our results.
- Be informed and aware about the project.

Therefore, all the communication actions implemented during the project will ultimately direct traffic to the website, with the objective of increasing our “conversion rate”, which is the number of users or website visitors to take a desired action.

The website will be constantly improved throughout the duration of the project, based on Google Analytics and Google Webmaster Tools (including search engine optimisation - SEO).

The main features of the website are the following:

- **Responsive:** The website platform will suit different devices such as mobile, tablet and desktop.

- **Social media sharing:** The website is prepared to share information with social media networks such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook.
- **Mailing list subscription:** The website will have available a submission form for newsletter subscription requesting the name and email of the person subscribing.
- **Registration in BIAS activities:** The website will allow users to register to the upcoming BIAS activities, like the co-creation workshops and the raising awareness sessions.

The BIAS website will be an ongoing task and its structure will dynamically evolve together with the project during its lifespan.

In parallel, there have been ongoing discussions with the AI-on-Demand management board regarding the possible integration/link between BIAS website and the platform, which is currently supported by the AI4Europe project.

5.5.1.1 Settings

The URL (Uniform Resource Locator) defined for the website is www.biasproject.eu, which focuses both on the name of the project as its main component.

The domain selected was .eu because of its relevance at the European level and in reference to the fact that it is a European funded project.

5.5.1.2 Splash Page

A landing page or splash page for the BIAS project, was developed by LOBA at an early stage, by month 3 (January 2023). It served as a general introduction to the project while the main website was under development. The page featured the teaser video of the project, a brief introduction of the project, its main goals, action plan, beneficiaries, the consortium, contact information, and EU emblem. This Splash Page was developed under this URL: www.biasproject.eu.

Print screens of the Splash Page available in [Annex 6](#).

5.5.1.3 Official website

BIAS' website is a public project website and therefore authorised for public dissemination. It will allow world-wide access to the project's main materials and reports (that are authorised for public dissemination), and it will allow external parties to express their interest in the project. It will be continually updated during the project and kept active for at least 2 years after project-end.

The website will be launched in Month 5 (March 2023). It will use WordPress as back-office and the front-end will be all designed and customised to the project's identity and needs.

The website will be also regularly updated with news, events, relevant findings, achievements, and content extracted from the deliverables and reports. Regular maintenance of the website will be conducted.

5.5.1.3.1 Website sitemap

The website will feature the following structure:

Figure 4: BIAS Site Map

The main sections of the website include:

Table 4: BIAS website main sections

<p>Homepage</p>	<p>The Homepage will be creatively but objectively designed to showcase the project and attract the visitor to explore the other pages of the website. Four big objectives for the homepage are: i) promote the registration in our national labs ii) promote the registration to BIAS activities iii) provide visible access to social media iv) provide easy access to subscribe the newsletter. The Homepage contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Header: with the project logo and claim, the menu, and the search bar. • Main banner: with the BIAS mission, call of action that will direct to “Project overview” and social media icons. • BIAS teaser video (replaced with a more detailed one once finished). • National Labs registration. • “What we are doing”: boxes with links to the activities, results, events, and press corner pages.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter subscription. • Link to BIAS helix. • Footer: with the site map, “contact us” that will link to the Contact page, social media icons, link to the newsletter, EU flag and disclaimers, link for the Cookie Policy and Privacy Policy, and LOBA acknowledgement.
About us	<p>Page presenting the values and objectives of BIAS. Subpages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project overview: summary of the challenge addressed by the project, its mission, and specific objectives. • Action Plan: the methodology and main activities of the project. • Consortium: present the 9 partners composing the consortium with a dedicated page for each of them. • Advisory Board: information about each member from the Advisory Board. • Related Projects: description of related projects and initiatives and linkage to their websites.
Media	<p>Section for news and articles, events related to the project, and newsletters. Subpages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News and articles: press releases, press clipping, and articles written by the consortium. • Newsletters: subscription to the newsletter and links to the newsletters written. • Events: description of upcoming and past events. • Digital Repository: with picture gallery, video gallery and BIAS visual identity.
Results	<p>Repository of all Actionable Knowledge materials produced, reports compiled and other downloadable materials, as well as the storage of all BIAS public deliverables. Subpages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications: all the scientific papers written by the consortium can be read and downloaded through this subpage. • Public reports: BIAS public deliverables. • Other materials: factsheets, infographics, promotional videos, presentations, brochures, training materials, reports.
Activities	<p>Registration to BIAS activities - co-creation workshops, capacity building sessions and raising awareness sessions, with the description of each activity and registration to the sessions.</p>

National labs	Section where stakeholders can fill in the consent form to be part of a National Lab.
Contact	Contact form.

Other interfaces may be added/changed to the website according to the new project needs identified during its duration. The interface that refers to the National Labs, for example, will be removed or adapted once the registration for them will be closed.

The website will be permanently linked to and publicised on other relevant websites, a reciprocal arrangement to ensure maximum exposure. LOBA will develop and manage a referencing and Link Exchange Strategy to register the website on the major search engines and directories.

Throughout the whole website, particular attention will be paid to a great user experience. Examples: clickable logo to the homepage, selected items of the menu are highlighted. Furthermore, BIAS website will have an accessibility menu, bringing the inclusion and equality dimensions of the project into its own website.

5.5.1.3.2 Analytics and monitoring

The BIAS website will use Google Analytics as its web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help optimise the website and the communication and dissemination strategy. Furthermore, the monitoring process will ensure compliance with GDPR.

Relevant statistics that will be monitored are the following:

- Number of visitors.
- Time spent on the website.
- Returning visitors.
- Number of countries.

5.5.1.3.3 Web development process

The creation of the website followed a specific process to ensure its quality. Firstly, an internal meeting with LOBA’s technicians was conducted to present the briefing with all the features for the website that were being simultaneously presented and discussed with the consortium.

Until Month 4 LOBA will develop a wireframe of the website that will be shared with the consortium to show the overall structure of the website and identify any need for alterations or adjustments. In parallel, the contents for the website are being developed, in collaboration with BIAS partners for specific sections.

Then, LOBA will work on the design of the different pages, the front-end development (HTML) of the website, and finally, the development of the back-office of the website.

After each stage of development, a Quality Assurance (QA) procedure will be implemented, allowing detecting issues to be corrected. The designer, front-end developer and back-office programmer will validate their respective areas. Afterwards, two additional Quality Assurance tests will be conducted by other people from LOBA. After the final validations, the website will be ready to go online, replacing the Splash Page, under the official domain: www.biasproject.eu.

After the launch, the website will be still in a “stabilisation” phase for a few days, where any additional modifications or improvements can be identified and implemented. Thus, when the website is presented to the consortium, LOBA can consider suggestions and modifications when necessary.

5.5.2 Social Media

BIAS’ official social media pages have already been created but they don’t have any contents yet. They include [Twitter](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#). A [YouTube channel](#) was also created to serve as a repository of the project’s videos. The objective of these social media channels is to increase awareness, visibility to stakeholders, redirect to the website and reach for all activities as support to the creation of a large community.

The handle of the project is the same for all the channels: @BIASProjectEU. For setting up the social media accounts, image banners were designed for the page profile, together with template images that will be used for the posts and that should concisely but clearly inform about the scope of the project. The EU emblem and disclaimer is clearly visible in compliance with the EU guidelines for Horizon Europe projects.

Starting from M4, the social media pages of the project will be updated on a weekly basis with posts concerning the project’s latest updates, activities, and materials, as well as relevant news and articles regarding the project or posts that tackle common themes. Relevant results will be also communicated in a digestible way as “results in brief”. The dissemination of actionable knowledge and results in brief on social media channels will be more effective and potentially have better engagement rates.

Some ideas for the posts are the following:

- Events: awareness raising webinars, co-creation events, Helix events, summer schools, capacity building events, workshops, conferences, consortium meetings.
- Activities: expert interviews, surveys, Trustworthy AI Helix, ethnographic interviews, E-learning MOOC.
- Newsletters: 7 in total.
- Promotional and educational videos: promotional video of the project, mini-videos on the themes “What constitutes BIAS”, “How BIAS are experienced”, “How to recognise BIAS” - 5 in total.
- Articles and News.
- Results: scientific publications, public results, and other materials.
- Registration in the National Labs.

- Registration in the co-creation workshops, capacity building sessions and raising awareness sessions.
- Consortium presentation.
- Splash page launch.
- Launch of the website.

For this, LOBA creates a monthly social media plan with the copy, hashtags, mentions and images/videos per post. Although the social media plan is developed a month in advance, any additional posts that are needed can always be added. In the first months of the project, only one post per week will be developed (excluding additional retweets and shares), and after that, once the project has more content to disseminate, we will start doing two posts per week.

To involve the partners in the communication of the project and to make sure that all the new contents and results that are being developed within each WP have the due prominence in the BIAS social media, a Google Form was created ([Annex 5](#)), which will be shared monthly with the consortium. Through this form, each partner can share which new contents could be published in the networks. After a review and curation of these contents, they are organized according to their priority and contemplated in the next monthly plan.

Posts related to the project and its results may, when possible and relevant, mention some of the following accounts to increase reach:

- To communicate events, activities and/or project results (especially these) - @CORDIS_EU
- General information about Horizon Europe: @HorizonEU
- Linked to the topic of AI: @COE4AI, @DigitalEU
- The open access publishing platform of the EC: @OpenResearch_EU

Additionally, we will follow the following pages (and others):

- Related projects and initiatives channels:
 - @AI4EU
 - @RoboticsEU
 - @eu_trinity
 - @RobotUnion_EU
 - @AcrobaProject
 - @eu_harmony
 - @robs4crops
- BIAS sister projects:
 - AEQUITAS (still doesn't have social media)
 - FINDHR (still doesn't have social media)
 - MAMMOth (still doesn't have social media)
- Consortium partners social media channels (table 5)

As well as the hashtags:

- #HorizonEU

- #AI
- #bias
- #technology
- #equality
- #fairness
- #debiasing
- #inclusion
- #hiring
- #trustworthy
- #diversity
- #recruitment
- #market
- #labourmarket
- #HR
- #HRM

Partners are encouraged to use their own (institutional or personal) social media pages to boost BIAS, by sharing BIAS' website and social media pages, and using BIAS' handles whenever posting content related to the project through their own channels. Partners have already shared their personal accounts (not included in this deliverable due to privacy concerns), as well as the organisation's social media accounts, which are listed below:

Table 5: Organisations' social media URL

Organisations' social media URL				
Partner	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	Youtube
NTNU	https://www.facebook.com/ntnu.no	https://twitter.com/NTNU	https://www.linkedin.com/school/ntnu/	https://www.youtube.com/user/ntnuinfo
BFH	https://www.facebook.com/bernerfachhochschule	https://twitter.com/bfh_hesb	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bfh-technik-und-informatik/	https://www.youtube.com/user/BernerFachhochschule
LOBA	https://www.facebook.com/LOBA.cx	https://twitter.com/loba_cx	https://www.linkedin.com/company/loba-cx/mycompany/verification/	https://www.youtube.com/user/LOBACx

HI	https://www.facebook.com/HaskoliIslands	https://twitter.com/uni_iceland	https://www.linkedin.com/school/h%C3%A1sk%C3%B3li-%C3%ADslands/	-
CHX	https://www.facebook.com/crowdhelix/	https://twitter.com/crowdhelix/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/crowdhelix/	-
SVEN	https://www.facebook.com/SmartVeniceIT	-	-	-
LEIDEN	https://www.facebook.com/UniversiteitLeiden	https://twitter.com/eLaw_Leiden	https://www.facebook.com/UniversiteitLeiden	-
DIGI	-	https://twitter.com/digiotouch	https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiotouch-ou/	https://www.youtube.com/@digiotouch
FARPLAS	https://www.facebook.com/farplas/	-	https://www.linkedin.com/company/farplas/	https://www.youtube.com/c/Farplasotomotiv

All social media visuals will be cohesive and showcase the project’s identity. Therefore, LOBA will design, create, and animate tailored banners, illustrations, GIFs, graphics (etc.) whenever necessary, for posts, or social media profile and cover images distributed in accordance with the BIAS communication plan. Some templates to use on social media are available in [Annex 7](#).

Paid campaigns (ads) will be built around three core goals:

1. Enlarge and engage the community.
2. Build an email contact list.
3. Increase website traffic.

Facebook and Twitter campaigns will unfold whenever BIAS has important milestones/deliverables/achievements to announce. Social Media statistics will be closely and regularly

monitored and analysed, to identify any need for improvement, or adjust the strategy implemented for each target group.

5.5.3 Videos

LOBA will develop a BIAS promotional video (What is BIAS project?) by Month 7 to be shared on the project's digital channels and used to promote the project or introduce it at events, following the steps below:

1. Conceptualisation: creation and development of the strategy and concept idea.
2. Pre-Production: development of the final version of the script and preparation of the technical script as well as the creation of storyboard and mood board.
3. Production: turning the script into interactive material using Filming & Digital Cinematography, Production – Video & Audio editing, Production – Graphics/2D/3D Animation.
4. Post-Production: joining of all the elements created in the different production areas, including VFX Production and “Colour Correction”.
5. Marketing & Distribution support: development of different multimedia outputs for content strategy support and the on-site and online promotion campaigns to start the distribution.

The project has already developed in Month 2 a teaser video of the project aimed at starting to create interest and awareness about the project and expectation about what's to come. This teaser video is already available in BIAS YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qLFGzum01F8>

Figure 5: Screenshot of BIAS teaser video

Besides these videos, LOBA will also create and produce a set of mini videos about:

- What constitutes biases
- How biases are experienced
- How to recognize them

These videos will be developed with the support of the partner BFH. They will have a focus on citizen advocacy organizations and educators.

5.5.3.1 Webinars editing

During the KoM, it was suggested that LOBA can edit the videos that will be recorded in the capacity building sessions conducted in BIAS by SVEN and will be edited by LOBA. This edition will consist of:

- Revising/cutting any parts related with technical or connection difficulties during the webinars.
- Adding a first frame with the animation of BIAS logo.
- Adding a second frame with the title, date, and speakers of the sessions.
- Adding a last frame with all the website, email, logos of partners, EU flag and funding disclaimer.
- Additional editing may be considered case by case.

These videos will then be used for the e-learning course to be developed on Month 36 and hosted on DIGI's MOOC platform. They will contain the most interesting and relevant sessions of the in-person capacity building sessions.

5.5.4 Communication Toolkit

The communication toolkit developed for the BIAS project comprises the materials that aid the consortium in their formal and informal communication activities, such as reporting and participation in meetings and events, while ensuring a promotion of the brand identity making it memorable.

This kit is composed by the project's stationery, promotional materials, and merchandising, as explained below.

5.5.4.1 Stationary

The stationery produced for the project includes materials to support the communication and reporting of the project, namely:

- Word and PowerPoint templates used for reporting purposes and for presentations at meetings or events, respectively (the PowerPoint has two formats: 16x9 and 4x3).
- Supporting materials for participating in events and meetings such as folders, letterhead paper, business cards, background for online meetings, and an email signature for the identification of the project in communications.

The first version of the materials can be seen in [Annex 8](#).

5.5.4.2 Promotional material

The project will develop during Month 5 materials for its promotion during the participation in or organisation of events and meetings with relevant stakeholders.

These materials include:

- Brochure with information about the objectives, activities and expected results of the project.
- Flyers to explain the project's mission in a succinct way.
- Poster, roll-up, and pop-up stand to increase the project's visibility in events.

5.5.4.3 Merchandising

Goodies or merchandising will be distributed at events with the purpose of brand promotion and brand awareness. Goodies are also a technique used to attract visitors to the booth and use that as an

opportunity to create awareness about the project's objectives or engage them in the project's activities and events. Goodies will include BIAS' logo, URL, and claim.

These materials have not been thought out at this point, but from Month 4 these will start to be defined for the first BIAS events/activities.

5.5.5 Press Releases

During the project, press releases will be sent to specific media outlets and relevant stakeholders to inform them about important achievements, activities, results, and events. A first press release will be sent to media outlets on Month 7 to present the project and the launch of BIAS' website.

LOBA will make use of over 10.000 contacts of journalists which is an asset for press release distribution to ensure wide media coverage, which can be configured for geo-specific campaigns. This list will also be adapted according to the result to be communicated, the area of expertise in which it is inserted and the target audience to whom we want to send the information.

For ensuring local dissemination, partners are encouraged to also distribute the PR in their own languages to relevant media from their countries.

5.5.6 Newsletter and mass mailing

BIAS will distribute a newsletter every 7 months. The consortium will contribute to the development of the contents, and LOBA will ensure the mass distribution of the newsletters to the list of subscribers (complying with GDPR).

The newsletters will be sent proactively to website subscribers, other synergy projects and partners will also actively share the newsletters with their own contacts in both a personal and professional level. More information on how partners can support the communication and dissemination of the project in section 5.3.

Each newsletter will communicate the main project news, events, and results in an understandable manner to the project's subscribers. It can include articles, interviews, videos and infographics and it will be uploaded to the public section of the website. It will also promote the registration in the National Labs and project activities (such as the co-creation workshops, capacity building sessions and raising awareness sessions).

LOBA will keep track and analyse newsletter statistics based on the number of recipients that have subscribed and unsubscribed, the number of newsletters opened, and the number of clicks.

The website includes an area to subscribe to the newsletter, and the system used for managing and distribution of newsletters is Zoho Campaigns. The newsletters will also be promoted through BIAS social media.

To maximise the impact of the newsletter, the date for launching the first newsletter will be decided based on the progress of the project and the information that we would like to transmit to our target groups and stakeholders. As a preliminary date, the 1st newsletter will be launched in Month 7.

To complement the distribution of newsletters, the project will also send mass mailing with relevant announcements or achievements like events, or surveys.

The project will also proactively contribute to the newsletter from other projects with similar goals and target groups as BIAS, to increase visibility and reach.

Aside from the newsletters, direct email will also be sent to the subscribers to communicate individual/specific activities/events regarding the project as many times as it is necessary. These direct emails will be sent proactively to subscribers. LOBA will also create special communication for members of National Labs updating on the impact of their participation.

5.5.7 Scientific dissemination

BIAS will publish at least 12 scientific articles in leading journals in the realm of computer science, AI, worker studies, etc. Journals to target include:

Table 6: Journals where to publish BIAS scientific articles

JOURNAL	IF
Big Data & Society	5.97
Ethics and Information Technology	4.45
Information, Communication, & Society	5.42
Internet and Higher Education	7.18
Journal of Information Technology	9.44
New technology, Work and Employment	4.23
Science, Technology and Human Values	4.51
Technovation	6.66
CoDesign	1.89
Gender, Work and Organization	3.47
Information and Society	4.48
Journal of Career Development	2.54
Nature Machine Intelligence	15
Science, Technology, and Society	4.19
Work, Employment and Society	5.33

OpenAIRE and Zenodo channels will be used as well, and the DOI of the article will be included in the OpenAire repository.

Partners must acknowledge the project using the phrase “Funded by the European Union” or “This [work/paper/event...] was supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation

programme under grant number 101070468 - BIAS”, accompanied by the EU emblem. Papers and publications should be uploaded to Zenodo.

5.5.8 Activities and events

In this project we can differentiate between “internal” and “external” events.

The “internal events” refer to the events that will be organised during the project under the frame of specific work packages (WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7). These “internal events” have their specific purposes for technical aspects of the project, but they are also a good opportunity for communicating and disseminating the project. In this context, WP7 will support the partners in communicating these events, engaging potential participants, and disseminating the outcomes from those events.

The strategy and methodology of the internal events are currently being defined under the respective WPs therefore the following information is subject to alteration:

Table 7: BIAS individual events

Individual events						
Partner	Event/Activity	#	Target number of participants	Target group	Country	Date
All*	Physical Co-creation	14	490	CS, Advocates	All except IE, PT	M7-15
All*	Digital co-creation	6	300	CS, Advocates	Pan-European	
CHX	Helix events	3	300	All	EE, IT, NO*	M12-36
SVEN	Awareness Raising events	3	300	CS, Advocates	Pan-European	M12-24
DIGI	Summer school on debiasing AI systems	1	35	KP	EE	M22
All	Capacity building events	18	630	KP, CS	All	M28-38
LEID	Regulatory acceptability workshop	1	15	CS	Belgium*	M46
CHX	Closing conference	1	150	All	The Netherlands	M48
Total		41	2.220	*Tentative + All except CHX, LOBA		

5.5.8.1 Events’ communication “before, during and after”

The communication and promotion of BIAS events or partners’ participation in events will follow a specific strategy. These actions will be implemented in the promotion of the events, whenever applicable. They will be adjusted depending on the needs and type of involvement of BIAS (i.e., organiser, participant, attendee).

Communication BEFORE the event:

- Event upload on the website
- Event upload in the Trustworthy AI helix
- Design of cover image or banner, or other images/videos
- Social media campaign
- Publication in the newsletter
- Press release (if applicable)
- Mass mailing to BIAS mailing list
- BIAS partners dissemination through their networks and channels

Communication DURING the event:

- Social media coverage (photos/quotes sent to LOBA for posting)
- Networking and distribution of promotional materials

Communication AFTER the event:

- Article upload in website (conclusions, photos, presentations, recording, etc)
- Event recording uploaded in YouTube channel (for online events when applicable)
- Social media campaign
- Publication in the newsletter

In addition to events, BIAS has planned many activities that will engage external stakeholders as part of the project’s research strategy. They have the goal of either collecting information from stakeholders (expert interviews, survey, ethnographic interviews) or disseminating research findings (E-learning MOOC, Trustworthy AI Helix). These are also opportunities to communicate about the project more broadly and raise public awareness.

Table 8: BIAS non-event engagement activities

Non-event Engagement Activities					
Partner	Event/Activity	Participants	Target group	Country	Date
All*	Expert interviews	90	KP, CS	All	M1-3
LEID	Survey	4.000	CS, Advocates	Pan-European	M1-8
CHX	Trustworthy AI Helix	150	KP, CS	Pan-European	M7-48
NTNU, HI	Ethnographic interviews	365	All	IS, IT, NL, NO, TR	M7-32
SVEN	E-learning MOOC	500	All	Pan-European	M40-48
TOTAL		5.105	*All, except CHX, LOBA		

The “external events” refer to events organised by others to disseminate the project. Workshops, booths, and networking events are important for increasing the project’s awareness within specific target groups and present the project’s mission, activities, and results. This includes for example workshops and cluster meetings arranged by the EC, other projects/initiatives, and European fairs/exhibitions.

The following table provides possible events that will be considered:

Table 9: External conferences and similar events

Conferences and similar events
AAAI/ACM conference on AI, Ethics and Society
ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (ACM FAccT)
COLING (International Conference on Computational Linguistics)
Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems and the Queer in AI workshop at NeurIPS
4S: Society for Social Studies of Science
Human Factors in Computing Systems
Human-Robot Interaction (ACM HRI)
IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Applications
IEEE International Conference on Robot & Human Interactive
Nordic Work Environment Conference
The European Conference for Social Work Research
Annual Summit of AI for Good

5.6 Networking and clustering

5.6.1 Related projects and initiatives

As part of BIAS’ effort to enhance our dissemination and communication plan and to maximize the impact of the project, we intend to establish a clustering plan and collaboration system with existing networks and ecosystems (existing partnerships/projects and initiatives, etc.), as well as relevant HEU projects that are related to the BIAS objectives and scope.

These are BIAS clustering objectives:

- Discuss technical information between the projects/initiatives to advance the mitigation of diversity biases in AI to better meet EC expectations.
- Amplify the impact of the communication and dissemination activities by creating synergies between the communication teams of the different projects.
- Improve the exploitation and innovation ecosystem that facilitates follow-up to other R&D activities, particularly through the Trustworthy AI Helix.
- Explore the potential for synergies between partners of different consortiums and other related stakeholders.
- Work towards the EC’s ambition of an integrated collaborative approach between different HEU projects and related initiatives.

Table 11 presents an early list of existing projects/initiatives related to BIAS and potential collaboration opportunities:

Table 10: Existing projects/initiatives related to BIAS

Clustering	Theme	Coordinator
Sister Projects		
AEQUITAS	AEQUITAS project will develop a controlled experimentation environment to help AI producers to increase awareness of bias produced by AI systems and evaluate and (possibly) repair existing AI systems.	UniBo (IT)
FINDHR	FINDHR project will facilitate the prevention, detection, and management of discrimination in algorithmic hiring and closely	UNIVERSIDAD POMPEU FABRA (ES)

	related areas involving human recommendation.	
MAMMOth	MAMMOth project tackles bias by focusing on multi-discrimination mitigation for tabular, network and multimodal data.	CERTH (GR)
Related Projects/Initiatives		
iRECS	iRECS will first scan and map existing needs raised by new and emerging technologies in European and global research ethics communities. Second, it will produce and implement training materials for European and global audiences in research ethics communities. Third, it will conduct and permanently establish training programmes. Fourth, it will propose adaptations to the research ethics process in Europe.	Universitat Bonn (DE)
SHERPA	SHERPA project will investigate, analyse and synthesise our understanding of the ways in which smart information systems (SIS; the combination of artificial intelligence and big data analytics) impact ethics and human rights issues.	University de Montfort (UK)
SIENNA	The SIENNA project addressed ethical issues in three new and emerging technology areas: human genomics, human enhancement and human-machine interaction.	University Twente (NL)
Panelfit	PANELFIT is a H2020 EU funded project aiming at facilitating the adaptation processes between new technical advances and	UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO (ES)

	legal frameworks, by producing a set of editable, openly accessible guidelines, as well as offering operational standards capable of reducing ethical and legal problems posed by information and communication technologies.	
TechEthos	TechEthos project will review emerging technologies and the ethical issues these raise.	AIT (AT)
AI4EUROPE	The EU-funded AI4EUROPE project, in collaboration with AI4EU and other related projects, aims to develop this space by introducing an unbiased, open and cooperative platform from and for the European research community for excellent studies of AI	UCC (IE)
NoBIAS	NoBIAS will develop novel methods for AI-based decision making without bias by considering ethical and legal considerations in the design of technical solutions. The core objectives of NoBIAS are to understand legal, social, and technical challenges of bias in AI-decision making, to counter them by developing fairness-aware algorithms, to automatically explain AI results, and to document the overall process for data provenance and transparency.	UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER (DE)
Adra-e	Adra-e supports the AI, Data and Robotics Association and Partnership to create the conditions for a sustainable European ecosystem	INRIA (FR)

CHX, in collaboration with the project coordinator, will engage with the identified projects to establish relevant synergies between the stakeholders involved. This mapping exercise will continue to be updated by CHX in collaboration with the BIAS consortium partners throughout the duration of the project.

5.6.2 Joint Clustering Board

CHX, in collaboration with the project coordinator, will engage with the sister projects coordinators and invite them for a network meeting. Following the meeting, the 4 projects will develop a Joint Clustering Board and Plan that will include the following activities:

- Creation of a common identity (logo),
- Mailing list,
- Promotion of sister projects on BIAS website,
- Yearly meetings,
- Invitation to BIAS events.

The other projects and initiatives identified, and other relevant ones will be approached by CHX to establish synergies and support towards relevant activities. The Clustering Board will include one key representative from each one of the partner projects and will coordinate the clustering activities of these projects. It will convene and communicate regularly, and a common identity (including logo and templates for communication and reporting) will be developed as well as KPIs to frame the collaboration. An indicative timeline of activities will be compiled and updated throughout the duration of BIAS and will frame the collaboration between the projects.

Figure 6: BIAS Clustering Plan

5.6.3 Trustworthy AI Helix

A virtual community called the Trustworthy AI Helix will be created and populated with consortium members, with a target of more than 150 organisations being members of the Helix by M48. This community will include relevant stakeholders creating a self-sustainable ecosystem for the project.

The Helix will be used as a main dissemination tool. Through this virtual Helix community, the project’s stakeholders will be made aware of BIAS’ research outputs. The Trustworthy AI Helix will continue to exist even after the project has finished as a self-sustained community, focused on facilitating collaborative partnerships. A Helix Manager (CHX) will be responsible for onboarding new members, connecting the various stakeholders involved and maintaining the community active and featuring various opportunities for collaboration. The Helix Leadership will be taken over by NTNU. NTNU will help to steer the community by assisting CHX in understanding the thematic landscape, connecting with relevant stakeholders and initiatives, and providing support in the organisation of events.

A unique feature of the Crowdhelix platform is its matchmaking algorithm (recommender engine, see Figure 7) that adds value to both the Helixes and the organisations registered. This tool connects the posted opportunities with researchers and institutions possessing the required expertise or infrastructure. Once an organisation or an individual researcher registers for the Trustworthy AI Helix and profiles their expertise, the platform's recommender engine will help the Crowdhelix team flag their expertise to suitable, available opportunities within the Helix. The matchmaking algorithm can also be used to connect with various stakeholders and will be used to find specific collaborators for the project’s future needs.

Figure 7: Helix Recommender Engine

To draw on and steer this virtual ecosystem, CHX will organise 4 events (one per year) to bring the profiled organisations together and discuss topics of interest to both the Helix community and BIAS. Each Helix also holds topic-focused events and acts as a cross-sector and international collaboration platform for launching successful Horizon 2020 proposals. Crowdhelix will hold at least one major event each year, bringing together members of the network and outside experts to provide training, information, and insights regarding the Horizon Europe programme.

5.7 Project and Community Sustainability

5.7.1 Post-project Trustworthy AI Helix maintenance

The Trustworthy AI Helix will act as the collaborative ecosystem for maximizing the project impact as it will work as a privileged platform to enhance BIAS’ results dissemination and exploitation and ultimately its innovation potential. The virtual community extends beyond the BIAS project partners and will consist of stakeholders interested in using the outputs of the project and in exploiting them, ensuring its long-term sustainability. Crowdhelix commits to maintaining the Helix for at least 2 years after the project has concluded. When the project ends, the Helix will continue to be hosted on CHX’s platform, and everyone who joined during the project will be able to retain their accounts for free (as external organizations), as well as have the option for their organizations to join as full members on the network, thereby supporting long-lasting impact from the BIAS project.

5.7.2 Funding synergies for exploitation

In cooperation with Digiotech, Crowdhelix will also undertake an analysis of future funding opportunities aligned with the future plans of the project in order to ensure outputs entrance to the market and further development of the results achieved throughout the implementation of BIAS. The Trustworthy AI helix will generate opportunities for collaboration in the framework of Horizon Europe. Crowdhelix will foster the creation of new consortia to capitalize on the BIAS project and go beyond the project. BIAS consortium members will be invited to be part of new project consortia according to their expertise and willingness to be involved in new projects. Crowdhelix will facilitate this process by connecting BIAS consortium members with its network and through dedicated matchmaking events organized as part of its internal activities.

Figure 8: Crowdhelix Model

Academic as well as commercial exploitation of the developed intellectual properties (IP) are being planned in the BIAS project also in WP6. The Task 6.1 is compiling a list of background and potential foreground in terms of IP, their route to exploitation, and commercialisation potential. These will be described in detail in Deliverable D6.1. This section summarises the investment synergies and fund-raising roadmap for the commercially exploitable results of the BIAS project.

To sustain the innovations developed in the project, the partners led by DIGI will seek to raise additional investments for operational and commercial sustainability. A summary of the funding terminologies used in this deliverable is provided in [Annex 9](#).

Figure 9: Different fund-raising rounds

Typically, an innovation commercialisation draws three types of investments – (a) Angel Investment, (b) Venture Capitals funding early rounds of investment, and (c) Governmental grants. DIGI will utilise a combination of Angel Investment and government grants to sustain the beginning of commercialisation of the project results.

DIGI will initially perform an investment analysis encompassing IRR, ROI & ROE corresponding to BIAS project’s business plan in terms of assessing the maturity of results, their commercial credibility, associated risks, and potential for raising capital (e.g., seed funding, Series A). An assessment of investor readiness level (IRL) of the BIAS results will be performed to setup and implement a roadmap to improve the IRL to 6. Following that, this task will also develop funding synergies with additional funding mechanisms including ESIF, ERDF, ESF+, InvestEU, JTF, Digital Europe Programme, public funding, angel investing, venture capital. A non-exhaustive list of Angel Investors providing funding for AI and HR related technologies are provided below:

Name	Geographical reach	Website
European Angels Fund (EAF)	EAF is operational across Europe with dedicated national programmes for Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain alongside a pan-European allocation for Business Angels in other geographies and investing across the continent.	Link

Sofia Angels Ventures	Across Europe	Link
Caesar Business Angels		Link
European Business Angels Network		Link
Change Ventures	Baltic start-up seed fund	Link

6 Internal communication

To smooth the internal communication between the consortium partners, a repository in SharePoint was created, in order to manage and access to shareable documents:

- Procedures for reporting.
- Dissemination & Communication reporting Excel.
- Information for dissemination from each partner.
- Events participation Excel.

6.1 Reporting procedure

To guarantee a successful dissemination of the BIAS project as well as an efficient reporting process within the participant portal, partners are asked to fill in a form for monitoring the communication and dissemination activities and its impact.

The participant portal now has two areas, one for communication activities and another for dissemination activities. According to several EC guidelines¹, and information in the participant portal, the concepts of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are defined as follows.

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.	Objective
Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)	Focus
Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).	People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.	Target Audience

Figure 10: Slide from the EC presentation "Introduction to the concepts of Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation"

Communication activities are those aimed at promoting the action and its results. These activities require strategic and targeted measures for communicating about i) the action and ii) its results to a multitude of audience, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>

Therefore, communication activities are those that create awareness and inform about the project's objectives, scope and mission, activities, and results, and engage stakeholders to participate in events/activities.

Dissemination activities have a stronger focus on disseminating knowledge and results towards its actual use, in a targeted manner to specific beneficiaries or potential end-users, i.e., knowledge transfer, scientific publications, use or replicability of results/methodologies, lessons learned, data, etc.

In this sense, BIAS has developed an Excel that will be used by partners to report their D&C activities.

Screenshots from the Excel can be seen on [Annex 10](#).

7 Evaluation Criteria (KPIs)

In the Grant Agreement (GA) a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been described to monitor the performance of the activities of the project including dissemination and communication. Therefore, the table below shows the overview of all the Key Performance Indicators of the project as stated in the GA:

Table 11: BIAS evaluation criteria

ACTIVITY	AUDIENCE	KEY MESSAGE	RELATED KPI	M24	M48
Website (D&C)	All	Main online information hub, D&C of project results, news, events. Generated awareness on the project.	Website user	1500	3000
			Total page views	5000	10000
			Countries reached	10	20
Promotional materials	All	Facilitate reaching a broader audience.	Number distributed at events and meetings	1000	1500
Factsheets	All	Facilitate reach to broader audiences/disseminate project's activities, results, and impact.	Factsheets produced	3	8
Social Media (D&C)	All	Increasing visibility to stakeholders active on Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn, raising awareness and redirecting to the website.	Total followers	500	800
			Posts	60	80
			Clicks to the website through SoMe posts	100	250
Press Releases (D)	All, mainly advocates	Communication of project news, events, and results	Press releases distributed	2	3
Newsletters and Mailing List (C)	Key players and advocates	Communication of main project news, events, and results in an understandable manner to the project's subscribers. Create special	Mailing list subscribers	300	500
			Newsletters sent	2	5
			Newsletter views (in website)	150	250

		communication for members of national labs updating on the impact of their participation.	National lab e-mails	5	11
Promotional Videos (D)	All	Communication of the project's activities and USP in a captivating and engaging manner; to be used in awareness raising events, MOOC, final conference.	Number of videos	3	5
			Views: YouTube, SoMe, website	500	1000
			# of events presented at	4	7
Scientific Publications, White Papers (D)	Key players, context setters	Scientific validation of project's approach and findings, sharing of knowledge.	Papers published or submitted	4	12
Popular media articles (D)	All	Facilitate reach to broader audiences/ disseminate project's activities,			
results and impact.	Number of articles published	30	70		
External events (D)	Key players and advocates	Validation of project's approach and finding, dissemination of the project and its activities	Number of events attended to disseminate the project	8	20

8 Schedule & Timing

This section comprises a timeline for the launching of the main materials and tools for BIAS' dissemination and communication strategy. The timeline only includes the tools that will be produced in the first year, and will be updated during the project lifetime:

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Identity & Brand manual		X										
Stationery (Templates & supporting materials)		X										
Splash Page		X										
Social Media channels		X										
Teaser video		X										
Website					X							
Promotional Materials (Brochure, poster...)					X							
Promotional video							X					
1st Newsletter							X					
Press Release							X					

9 Conclusions

To successfully disseminate the BIAS project, a consistent brand with a strong mission, supported by useful tools, fed with attractive content, and driven by fully committed partners is the key. Therefore, LOBA will proactively encourage all partners to contribute and share information about the BIAS project at all levels to provide the best content possible and to increase the awareness of the project.

This document will be updated regularly during the project and the first Communication and Dissemination report will be provided on month 24 (Deliverable 7.3) and updated at Month 48 (Deliverable 7.4). A second version of the dissemination and communication plan will also be submitted on Month 24 (Deliverable 7.2 – Revised dissemination, exploitation, communication plan

10 Annexes

10.1 Annex 1 - Presentation of the identity and the concept

• logo proposal

• AI reference font
• Futuristic font

• "Softer" approach to AI
• AI as a tool and not as the focus of the project

• logo proposal

monument
extended

Logotype font

Only used in logo.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 TUVWXYZ

• logo proposal

neue
machina

Communication font

We use this font in running texts and titles.

abcdefghijklmnopqrs
tuvwxyz0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMN
OPQRSTUVWXYZ

• logo proposal

sizes and margins

safety margins

minimum size application

BIAS | 658x38px

In these cases the claim is removed for readability reasons

key visual
applications

• key visual applications

• key visual applications

thank you

10.2 Annex 2 – BIAS Brand Book

• BIAS - **logotype** - negative version

Negative version

The negative version should be used as an alternative in the positive version of the logo, when there is a need to use it on a dark background.

Do not use for marks whenever the legibility is affected.

This version could be used in different background colors: black, purple and green.

• BIAS - **logotype** - safety margins

Safety margins

The logo (positive version) should be placed on white to maintain the visual impact and maintain the integrity.

The margin must be respected. It is necessary to the width of a dot, more specifically (30/70%).

Safety margins ensure that external elements do not interfere with the readability of the brand.

Any graphic element foreign to our identity (including icons) must not surround the defined limit.

• BIAS - **logotype** - minimum sizes

	for screens	for printing
with claim		
without claim		

Minimum sizes

In every application, minimum dimensions for the brand name & mark for printed media, the minimum size for the brand name must be respected. In digital formats, the minimum size for the brand is 10 pixels wide.

colours

The BIAS identity is unique and funny. That's why it has a restricted color palette that represents and corresponds to the communication, both iconographically and semantically.

• BIAS - **shapes**

Gender, religion, sexual orientation and other characteristics are represented by mixing colours.

diversity using shapes

• BIAS - **shapes**

Gender, religion, sexual orientation and other characteristics are represented by mixing colours.

diversity using colours

BIAS - **colours** - colour palette

HTML 0076AF CMYK 00 58 00 0 RGB 144 118 175	HTML 50BC9E CMYK 53 0 42 0 RGB 128 188 158	HTML 242222 CMYK 75 64 59 77 RGB 33 34 34
HTML FCEA91 CMYK 2 5 58 0 RGB 252 234 145	HTML FFFFFFFF CMYK 0 0 0 0 RGB 255 255 255	

• BIAS - **colours** - principal colours

Main colours

These are the main colors of the brand. They should be used in the communication.

All the colors are designed to distinguish them. However, if they should be used together in one of the cases.

10.3 Annex 3 – Mapping of local/national/European actors

Most mapping activities are limited to the countries of the consortium members. However, some have begun to do wider mapping on a European scale or in organizations outside their country.

10.3.1 NTNU

Name of the actor	Target audience	Category within target audience	Potential project activities	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
European Association of People Management	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms		https://www.eapm.org	This is a European association for human resource professionals and organizations. Their exact competence area should be established following initial contact
HR Norge	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms		http://www.hrnorge.no	HR Norge is the European branch of EAPM
Jobbnorge	Key Players	Specific platforms using AI	Expert interview, capacity building, co-creation	jobbnorge.no	Jobbnorge is the website where all job openings in Norway are posted
Manpower Norge	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI	Expert interview, capacity building, co-creation	https://www.manpower.no/nb	The Norwegian branch of the online resume platform Manpower.
Norwegian Digitalisation Agency	Context Setters	Policy makers	Policymaking activities, ALTAI analysis	https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dep/kdd/organisation/etater-og-virksomheter-under-kommunal-og-moderniseringsdepartementet/Subordinate	The Norwegian Digitalisation Agency is part Ministry of Local Government and Regional Development. They direct digitalization policy, including authoring a recent “National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence

				agencies-and-institutions/digitalisering/sdirektoratet/id2684200/	
Nora AI	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	Expert interviews, industry involvement	https://www.nora.ai	Consortium of research organizations in Norway doing AI.
Unicorns in Tech	Key Players	New technologies developers	capacity building, general networking	https://www.unicornsintech.com	Unicorns in Tech is an advocacy group for LGBTQ+ people in the tech sector.
Uhlala Group	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	capacity building, general networking	https://www.uhlala.com/en/home/	Uhlala Group is the parent organization of Unicorns in Tech. They provide consulting services to companies on LGBTQ+ issues, including HR policies
Center for Language and Cognition, University of Groningen	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Expert interview, networking, maybe advisory board	https://www.rug.nl/research/clcg/?lang=en	This research group has a track record of research and public engagement of gender bias in NLP-AI
Norwegian Center for AI Innovation	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	National Lab membership, networking, co-creation activities	https://www.ntnu.edu/norwai	This center coordinates research and innovation activities among three universities, two research institutes and 11 companies. It works to consolidate and strengthen the Scandinavian applied AI communities
Nordic Tech Advocates	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	National lab membership, networking, capacity building	https://www.technordicadvocates.org	An incubator for tech startups, including running events for women in the tech community.

Oda Network	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	Networking, clustering, co-creation, capacity building	https://odanettverk.no/about-oda/	ODA is the leading meeting place for women in tech in the Nordics with more than 10.000 members and more than 50 strategic partners across various industries.
Nordic Centre for Sustainable and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence Research	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Networking, clustering, co-creation, capacity building	https://www.oslomet.no/en/nordstar	This is a Centre of Research Excellence in modern AI. One of its focus areas are "Human factors in AI"
OECD programme on AI in Work, Innovation, Productivity and Skills	Key players	Policymakers	Policymaking activities, ALTAI analysis	https://oecd.ai/en/work-innovation-productivity-skills	The OECD programme on AI in Work, Innovation, Productivity and Skills (AI-WIPS) analyses the impact of AI on the labour market, skills and social policy.
Crayon	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	expert advisory board, interview	www.crayon.com	Crayon ia a major global provider of digital IT services based in Norway. Their Compliance Office has previously been active in public engagement on issues of bias and ethics in AI

10.3.2 BFH

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Project activities in which they may be involved	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
Swiss Center for Augmented Intelligence SCAI	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Dissemination	http://www.swisscai.ch	Consortium of different Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences in the capital region of Switzerland working in the field of augmented rather than artificial intelligence, i.e., develop technologies that empower humans rather than replacing them.
Digital Responsibility ThinkTank	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Dissemination, awareness raising.	https://digitalresponsibility.ch/	Organizes yearly conference SHIFT (in German) w.r.t the topic of digital ethics. Also realize events like seminars, courses about the topic, and create guidelines.
Bern University of Applied Sciences - Institute New Work	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	National lab, scientific collaboration	https://www.bfh.ch/de/forschung/forschungsbereiche/new-work/	Researchers from Business School with strong interest in AI in HR, in particular Prof. Nada Endrissat, and Prof. Caroline Straub.
GRA Foundation against racism and antisemitism	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	Awareness raising, co-creation.	https://www.gra.ch/	Association fighting racism in Switzerland.

talent4gig	Key Players	New technologies developers	AI developers	https://www.talent4gig.com/	Company developing tools (potentially with AI) to assess skills of technical candidates in recruiting.
HR Praxis	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms		https://www.hrpraxis.ch/2022/04/hr-link-der-woche-ki-im-hr.html	Publisher in the HR, and AI in HR areas.
PwC	Key Players	New technologies developers		https://www.pwc.ch/en/insights/hr/the-benefits-of-using-artificial-intelligence-in-hr.html	Large company (consulting), with interest in AI in HR
HR Campus	Key Players	New technologies developers	Developers HR Software	https://www.hr-campus.ch/en/news-stories/artificial-intelligence-in-the-field-of-hr/	Company HR software
Polygon Software	Key Players	New technologies developers	Developers HR Software	https://polygon-software.ch/blog/wie-kuenstliche-intelligenz-das-personalmanagement-veraendert/	Company HR software
Agile HR Zurich Meetup	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	Dissemination, awareness raising.	https://www.meetup.com/zurich-agile-hr	Community with regular meetups. AI in HR was a topic of event in the past.
gggfon - gemeinsam gegen Gewalt und Rassismus	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	Awareness raising, co-creation.	https://www.gggfon.ch/	Association fighting racism in Switzerland.

Swiss Federation - Service for Combating Racism	Context Setters	Standardization organizations		https://www.edi.admin.ch/edi/en/home/fachstellen/frb.html	Governmental Office to combat racism in Switzerland
Swiss Federal Office for Gender Equality	Context Setters	Standardization organizations		https://www.ebg.admin.ch/ebg/en/home.html	Governmental Office for Gender Equality in Switzerland
Pink Cross	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	Awareness raising, co-creation.	https://www.pinkcross.ch/en	"Pink Cross is Switzerland's national umbrella organisation of gay and bisexual men* and represents their interests in all four language regions. We stand in for gay and bisexual men's interests in politics, administration, as well as the public. "
Solique	Key Players	New technologies developers	Developers HR Software	https://www.solique.ch/english/	Company HR software
Lionstep	Key Players	New technologies developers	Developers HR Software	https://www.lionstep.com/	Company HR software
Jacando	Key Players	New technologies developers	Developers HR Software	https://www.jacando.com	Company HR software

<p>Institute for Information Systems University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland</p>	<p>Advocates</p>	<p>Academics, researchers, and think tanks</p>	<p>Scientific collaboration</p>	<p>https://www.fhnw.ch/en/about-fhnw/schools/business/iwi</p>	<p>Recent work at the institute has concerned use of AI in HR systems in Switzerland</p>
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10.3.3 HI

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Project activities in which they may be involved	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
The Árni Magnússon Institute for Icelandic Studies	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	literary review, survey, national labs	https://www.arnastofnun.is/en/institute	Has researchers with a special focus on Machine Translation and AI
University of Iceland Department of Icelandic and Comparative Cultural Studies	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	literary review, survey, national labs	https://english.hi.is/faculty_of_icelandic_and_comparative_cultural_studies	Has a program on linguistics and language technology including machine learning and AI
Almannarómur	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	Survey	https://almannaromur.is/en	Almannarómur is a centre for language technology and responsible for implementing the Icelandic Language Technology Programme. The objective is to ensure the equal states of Icelandic in digital language technology
CADIA - Center for Analysis and Design of Intelligent Agents. RU	Key players	New technologies developers	Survey	http://cadia.ru.is/	CADIA is an interdisciplinary research center in artificial intelligence at the School of Technology and School of Social Sciences at Reykjavík University.
Opus futura	Key Players	Public and private investors	Survey	https://opusfutura.is/	HR managers and COOs between them and vast networks within the HR communities in the Nordics and Europe. Conducting a new approach to career development and job/workplace match.

50skills	Key Players	Public and private investors	Survey	https://www.50skills.com/	Hiring system that brings people, information and tools together
HR Monitor	Key Players	Public and private investors	Survey	https://hrmonitor.com/	HR monitor provides a human resource strategy and metrics to measure success. Text from their homepage: Using employee engagement software HR and business managers can focus more of their time on efforts that benefit the company directly. Automation is what makes regular measurements possible which helps managers keep their fingers on the pulse and proactively address issues while focusing on success.
FESTA	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	Survey	https://samfelagsabyrgd.is/en	Festa is a non-profit organization with over 170 associated members, which are combined mostly of Iceland's biggest to smallest companies, in addition to public organizations, universities, the City of Reykjavík and a few other municipalities. It focuses on sustainable development through the SDGs, climate change and corporate social responsibility in its broad sense.
Modul.work	Key Players	Public and private investors	Survey	https://www.modul.work/	From their homepage: Module work runs a job specification platform which enables every employee to shape and develop their job to fit their individual needs. This is an interactive and transparent software-as-a-Solution making it scalable and suitable for a hybrid workplace.

MÍÐEIND	Key Players	New technologies developers	Survey	https://xn--mieind-qwa.is/english.html	A startup company specializing in Language Technology, Natural Language Processing and Artificial Intelligence applications for the Icelandic language.
University of Reykjavík Department of Computer Science	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	literary review, survey, national labs	https://en.ru.is/st/dcs/graduate-study/msc-language-technology/	Has a program on Artificial Intelligence and Language Technology

10.3.4 CHX

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
AI Ireland	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://aiireland.ie/about/	AI Ireland is a non-profit community devoted to promoting AI in Ireland. AI Ireland through the use of AI Awards aims to increase public awareness of artificial intelligence (AI) and bring academia and industry together to showcase the excellent work done on the island of Ireland.
Kinesense	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.kinesense-vca.com/about/	In 2009, Mark and Sarah set out to solve a needle in a haystack problem: how to find critical evidence hidden in thousands of hours of video. The time and effort required to retrieve, view, analyse and report on video footage as evidence is a huge drain on resources. CCTV needed a new strategy, a new model and new tools. Kinesense was born to help get actionable intelligence from video faster.
SeamlessCare	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://seamlesscare.ie/	To use Empathic app simply record the non-verbal person for up to 10 seconds. The artificial intelligence in the app will interpret that vocalisation and predict which emotion the non-verbal person is expressing.
SoapBox	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.soapboxlabs.com/about/	Inspired by her oldest child and her background as a speech engineer at companies like IBM and Bell Labs, Patricia Scanlon, PhD founded SoapBox Labs in 2013 to redefine how children interact with technology using their voices.
Webio	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.webio.com/contact/	Bringing Artificial Intelligence driven conversations to the enterprise. Our conversational interface uses AI to streamline inbound and outbound customer communications across new and existing channels. Introducing chatbots, machine learning and conversational commerce for the contact centre.

RDI Hub	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://rdihub.com/	A world-class centre for design-led, innovation. A place for Organisations to Connect, Co Create and Scale.
Science Foundation Ireland	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.sfi.ie/	Our research promotes and assists the development and competitiveness of industry, enterprise and employment in Ireland. Oriented basic research is research that is carried out with the expectation that it will produce a broad base of knowledge that is likely to form the background to the solution of recognised, or expected, current or future problems or possibilities.
SFI Centre for Research Training in Artificial Intelligence	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.crt-ai.ie/	The SFI Centre for Research Training in Artificial Intelligence aims to create an internationally connected and globally recognised centre of excellence for the training of postgraduate students and the up-skilling of industry-based staff in key technical topics in artificial intelligence and data analytics.
Artificial Intelligence Association of Ireland (AIAI)	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	http://aiai.ucd.ie/	(AIAI) is a representative association for the Artificial Intelligence community in Ireland. AIAI promotes research, application, and understanding of Artificial Intelligence and has membership from academia and industry covering the whole island, encompassing areas such as general AI, machine learning, and data mining.
Irish Institute of Digital Business	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://iidb.ie/	The Irish Institute of Digital Business is an institutional research centre located in Dublin City University. It was established in December 2018 with the vision for the research centre is to be an internationally recognised centre of excellence for theoretical and applied research that investigates and accelerates the adoption of digital technologies and the transformation of business using these technologies.

ServisBot	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://servisbot.com/	By understanding natural language and executing business workflows, our AI bots can either fully or partially automate different customer interactions and journeys.
TechIreland	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.techireland.org/about	TechIreland is an independent not for profit on a mission to promote Irish and Ireland based innovation to the world through data, content and community activities. Set up in January 2017, TechIreland has made Ireland's startup ecosystem visible and tangible to all stakeholders for the very first time.
CeADAR	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://ceadar.ie/	CeADAR is Ireland's national centre for applied AI CeADAR offers a comprehensive service in all aspects of innovation and applied R&D in AI, Machine Learning and Data Analytics.

10.3.5 SVEN

Name of the actor	Target audience	Category within the target audience	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
VEDRAI	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://vedrai.com	Vedrai SpA is specialized in Artificial Intelligence and develops solutions to support entrepreneurs and managers in the decision-making process.
Inda	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://inda.ai/en/	Inda is a proprietary artificial intelligence technology for data analysis and interpretation created specifically for the HR world and designed to optimise the recruiting process. Through Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms, Inda helps recruiters to identify and attract the best possible talent.
SECO	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.seco.com/it/azienda/chi-siamo	SECO is a center of excellence in the field of innovation and technological integration. For over forty years, the company has been operating in the high-tech market, designing, developing and manufacturing cutting-edge proprietary technological solutions for industrial customers.
ALBA robot	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.clearbox.ai/product	Clearbox AI helps companies unlock AI and Analytics projects through the generation of high-quality synthetic data. Its solutions solve privacy issues to comply with the most recent regulations and facilitate data access and sharing inside and outside organisations. Synthetic data also helps mitigate data scarcity and problems surrounding AI model generalisation. The start-up provides extensive reports and metrics to verify the assets' quality and privacy profile with a data-centric approach.

indigo.ai	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://indigo.ai/en/	Indigo.ai is a full-service conversational AI platform to design and build beautiful chatbots, scale AI applications, analyze conversational experiences.
Arisk	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.arisk.it/pagina/la-nostra-mission	ARISK is an innovative startup which develops algorithms able to measure every kind of risk in an objective and comparable way in time and space.
Revelis	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.revelis.eu/#solutions	Revelis is an innovative SME that offers Artificial Intelligence solutions for Big Data analysis, multi-dimensional correlation, operation scenarios prediction and business processes optimization. Revelis solutions exploit machine learning and deep learning approaches in combination with automated reasoning and answer set programming, and implement explanation techniques to support decision-makers in Artificial Intelligence models understanding.
SB Italia	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.sbitalia.com/en/	By supporting companies determined to innovate and grow, SB Italia designs, develops and provides best-of-breed IT services and solutions that enable new business models, optimize the management of day-to-day processes and streamline IT expenditure.
Experis	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.experis.it/it	Experis is an IT provider. It provides IT consultancy and solutions, technical training and support to innovation professionals in their career paths.
Blue Tensor	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://bluetensor.ai/	it is first Italian development team that helps companies in automating processes and optimizing business management costs through AI solutions developed around specific problems without pre-packaged solutions. .
Opstar	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://www.opstart.it/it/home	It is the first Italian equity crowdfunding community for innovative and sustainable investments.

Crowdinvest	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://crowdinvestitalia.it	It is an Italian platform of equity crowdfunding
Veneto Region - Direzione ICT e Agenda Digitale	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://www.regione.veneto.it/web/guest/direzione-ict-e-agenda-digitale	It is the regional office in charge of the ICT strategy of the region as well as of the funds in ICT and AI
Task Force IA	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://ia.italia.it/task-force/	The task force studies how the dissemination of Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions and technologies can affect the evolution of public services to improve the relationship between public administrations and citizens.
Ministero delle imprese e del Made in Italy	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://www.mise.gov.it/it/incentivi/fondo-per-interventi-volti-a-favorire-lo-sviluppo-delle-tecnologie-e-delle-applicazioni-di-intelligenza-artificiale-blockchain-e-internet-of-things	It is the Italian Ministry for entrepreneurship. It releases funds for the development of AI technologies
Ecosagile	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://ecosagile.com/ENG/	EcosAgile is an innovative software platform, dedicated to SMEs, for Human Resources Management and all People-centric processes.
UNI	Context Setters	Standardization organizations	https://www.uni.com	It is the Italian Standardisation Institute
AIDP - Associazione Italiana Direzione Personale	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.aidp.it	It is the Italian network of HR managers and professionals

Risorse umane HR	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.risorseumane-hr.it	RisorseUmane-HR.it is a project dedicated to those who work in the Human Resources sector. It disseminates informative content and offers online services to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, the creation of relationships and B2B opportunities.
Confindustria	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.confindustria.it/home	Confindustria is the main association representing manufacturing and service companies in Italy.
Jobtome	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://weare.jobtome.com/	Jobtome is a platform facilitating the match between job demand and offer.
Indeed	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://it.indeed.com/about	Indeed is a platform facilitating the match between job demand and offer.
Centri per l'impiego	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.anpal.gov.it/centri-per-l-impiego	Employment centers are public structures coordinated by the regions or autonomous provinces. They favor the meeting between demand and supply of work and promote active labor policy interventions.
Manpower	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.manpower.it/manpower-e-il-gruppo	ManpowerGroup is a leader in creating integrated solutions for matching job supply and demand and career development.
Umana	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.umana.it	UMANA is an employment agency
Department of Information Engineering, University of Padua	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.dei.unipd.it/en/departmen t/about-dei	Has a research program in AI, including specialists in gender and ethics in AI

University of Bologna Department of Computer Science	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://corsi.unibo.it/2cycle/artificial-intelligence/	Has an International Masters degree in AI, which includes mandatory courses on NLP and Ethics in AI
University of Bologna Business School	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.bbs.unibo.eu/master-fulltime/digital-technology-management-artificial-intelligence-2/	Has a Masters program in Artificial Intelligence and Innovation Management
CISL	Advocates	Individual workers	https://www.cisl.it	It is a trade union organization
CGIL	Advocates	Individual workers	https://www.cgil.it	It is a trade union organization
UIL	Advocates	Individual workers	https://www.uil.it	It is a trade union organization
UGL	Advocates	Individual workers	https://www.ugl.it/en/	It is a trade union organization
Arcigay	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://www.arcigay.it	Arcigay is the main Italian LGBTI non-for-profit organization, the largest in terms of number of volunteers and activists throughout Italy.
Naga	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://naga.it	It is a volunteering organization providing health, social and legal assistance to foreign citizens and are committed to defending the rights of all
Ufficio Nazionale Antidiscriminazioni Razziali	Context Setters	Policy makers at international level	https://www.unar.it/portale/web/guest/che-cos-e-unar	It is the office appointed by the Italian State to guarantee the right to equal treatment of all persons, regardless of their ethnic or racial origin, their age, their religious beliefs, their sexual orientation, their gender identity or fact to be people with disabilities.
Casa internazionale delle donne	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://www.casainternazionaledelledonne.org/chi-siamo/	A women's association that works to promote the culture of solidarity, the development and protection of the rights of the person of any nationality.

Alma Human Artificial Intelligence	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://centri.unibo.it/alma-ai/it/centro/presentazione	The Alma Mater Research Center for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence is an interdisciplinary hub that aims at aggregating and boosting the AI-based research activities that are present in many Departments of the University of Bologna, positioning the University of Bologna in AI research, education, innovation and societal impact at an international level, and approaching AI research from different complementary perspectives.
Interdepartmental Research Center for Artificial Intelligence	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://ai.uniupo.it/	The AI@UPO research center has been established in 2019, with the goal of being a center for the interdisciplinary studies concerning Artificial Intelligence (AI). Proponents of the initiative are researchers very active in the field of AI since several years. Every department of UPO has joined the center from the very beginning, providing a wide set of competences from Computer Science (the field where AI is actually born), to other hard sciences, economics, social studies, law, humanities, pharmaceutical and medical sciences.
ASGI - Associazione studi giuridici sull'immigrazione	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.asgi.it/servizio-antidiscriminazione/	ASGI is a social promotion association born from the intention of sharing the nascent legislation on immigration by a group of lawyers, jurists and scholars, which has, over time, contributed with its documents to the drafting of regulatory texts state and community legislation on immigration, asylum and citizenship, promoting the protection of rights towards foreigners in the political-parliamentary debate and in the work of the public authorities.

Centro diritti umani - unipd	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://unipd-centrodirittiumani.it/it/	The Human Rights Center is the structure of the University of Padua that deals with research, training and dissemination on the issues of human rights, democracy and peace.
Aidos	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://aidos.it/	AIDOS is an association that since 1981 has been working for the rights, dignity and freedom of choice of women and girls around the world. A gender perspective for sustainable development
Osservatorio Regionale Antidiscriminazione	Context Setters	Policy makers at international level	https://www.venetoimmigrazione.it/antidiscriminazione	The Regional Anti-Discrimination Observatory was established on 21 March 2013. The main objective of the Observatory is the promotion of actions aimed at preventing and contrasting discrimination based on race and ethnic origin.
ANDI - Associazione Nazionale Disabili Italiani	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://www.disabilitaitaliani.org/index.html	The association intends to promote new and professional proposals to allow disabled people to improve their quality of life, taking advantage of special agreements with companies that offer specific products for the various disabilities.
AIIA - Associazione Italiana per l'intelligenza artificiale	Advocates	Citizen groups and advocacy organizations	https://aixia.it/informazioni/	The Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AIxIA) is a non-profit scientific association, founded in 1988, with the aim of promoting research and dissemination of Artificial Intelligence techniques.
Laboratorio Nazionale di Artificial Intelligence and Intelligent Systems	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.consortio-cini.it/index.php/it/artificial-intelligence-and-intelligent-systems	The laboratory aims to create the foundations for an effective Italian ecosystem of artificial intelligence, inclusive of all skills and devoted to highlighting national excellence to strengthen the scientific and technological role of Italy in Europe and in the world.

Esselunga	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://www.esselunga.it/cms/homepage.html	Esselunga S.p.A. is an Italian company operating in large-scale distribution in northern and central Italy with supermarkets and superstores. It adopts AI systems for recruitment
Confcommercio Padova	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.ascompd.com/	It is an association representing retailers in Padova and the province
Confcommercio Venezia	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	www.confcommerciovenezia.it	It is an association representing retailers in Venice and the province
Faculty of Science, Scola Normale Superiore	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.sns.it/en/faculty-sciences	Has a research program on explainable AI and machine learning
Adlconsulting	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.adlconsulting.it/it/	Adl Consulting is a strategic consultancy, public affairs and institutional communication company specialized in lobbying, advocacy and change management activities. We have been supporting data-driven decision-making and promoting the Digital Lobbying methodology in the industry since 2012
Fondazione Ampio Raggio	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.fondazioneampioraggio.it/	The Foundation connects innovators and innovation accelerators to strengthen the offer and bring it to the markets. Ampioraggio creates an inclusive, innovative and innovative ecosystem, an incremental generator of work and economic and social wealth, with sustainable and replicable effects on the territories and on the country system. The Foundation creates new opportunities on the domestic and international market by generating socio-economic value for its members and promoting meetings between supply and demand aimed at implementing sustainable innovation initiatives

				through the sharing of ecosystem relationships and the pro-active involvement of businesses, of institutions and qualified professionals in their respective wide ranges of action and competence
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10.3.6 ULEID

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Project activities in which they may be involved	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
Netherlands Institute for Human Rights	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Literary review, survey, national labs	https://www.mensenrechten.nl/english	The Netherlands Institute of Human Rights is an independent monitoring human rights institute. It recently completed a report on the use of AI in employment contexts
Department of Social Psychology, Tilburg University	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	Literary review, survey, national labs	https://www.tilburguniversity.edu/	Has research specifically on the use of AI in assessment during employment recruitment
Interdisciplinary research hub on digitalization and society, Radbound University	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	National labs	https://ihub.ru.nl	Includes research on algorithmic accountability and the use of AI in employment settings

10.3.7 DIGI

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Project activities in which they may be involved	Website Link	Brief description (100 words max)
TalTech	Key Players	New technologies developers		https://taltech.ee/en/	Creators of digital innovations, Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech) is leading Estonia and the world towards a sustainable digital future with confidence. As a leader in science, technology, and innovation, the school maintains constant interaction with universities around the world, bringing together scientists, students, and entrepreneurs. TalTech is also the most international university in Estonia. Of the nearly 10,000 enrolled students, approximately 16% come from more than 100 different countries across the globe.
Metta Space	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	WP2 activities and stakeholder engagement	https://metta-space.com/	To make companies ready for the next generation of talent through gender equality, diversity and financial transparency

10.3.8 FARPLAS

Name of the actor	Type of target audience	Category within the target audience	Website Link
Sabancı University	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.sabanciuniv.edu/en/
Istanbul Technical University	Advocates	Academics, researchers, and think tanks	https://www.itu.edu.tr/en
TAYSAD	Context Setters	Professional networks and platforms	https://www.taysad.org.tr/en
Çoşkunöz	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.coskunuzholding.com.tr/en
ARYA (Women Investment Platform)	Key Players	Public and private investors	https://www.aryawomen.com/
Büyütech	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://buyutech.com.tr/
TOGG	Key Players	New technologies developers	https://www.togg.com.tr/en/
Kariyer.net	Key Players	Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyze data	https://www.kariyer.net/

Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality	Context Setters	Policy makers at international, national and local level	https://www.ibb.istanbul/en
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10.4 Annex 4 - Definition of some BIAS channels and tools

Activity	Definition
Helix events	Major events, both physical and virtual, to promote clustering activities
Summer school on debiasing AI systems	The partner Digiotech will host a summer school in debiasing AI at their headquarters in Tallin by M24 as part of the effort of generating interest in this business area.
Capacity building events	BIAS will have a capacity building program, both in person and online training formats. An initial capacity building session will target AI specialists within the consortium. A second cycle will be rolled-out at partner's country national levels targeting AI researchers, students, practitioners, and HR specialists both from academic and industry sectors. Finally, an EU-level e-learning course (in the form of MOOC) will be developed to ensure multiplying impact in terms of capacity building. The capacity building program will tentatively encompass the following contents: concept of gender and intersectionality, ethics, AI and gender biases, AI, and other diversity bias (race, class, and age), tools to prevent, identify and avoid bias in AI in recommender and personalization systems and algorithmic decision making.
Closing conference	A closing conference presenting findings related to all aspects of BIAS research that will appeal to all external stakeholders. The two-day event will have a KPI of 150 attendees
Expert interviews	A short, easy to follow interview guide supporting interviews of approximately 30 minutes will be created featuring questions regarding what the experts (AI developers and HR executives) view to be the most important issues with multiple choice responses allowing for further elaboration through open conversation.
Trustworthy AI Helix	A virtual community hosted on the Crowdhelix platform and populated with consortium members, with a target of more than 150 organisations being members of the Helix by M48. This community will include relevant stakeholders creating a self-sustainable ecosystem for the project.
Ethnographic interviews	These ethnographic interviews will consist of a total of 20 months of research stays (4 months x 5 countries), where PhDs and researchers will go into the action of the data gathered and see on site how recruitment processes move through

	<p>organizations. Ethnographic data will be collected through interviews, ideally in person, across 5 European countries with a target minimum of 365 informants.</p>
<p>Physical and digital co-creation</p>	<p>Within the first phase of the BIAS co-creation process, every partner will carry out 2 workshops with 35 stakeholders - AI specialists, researchers, students, practitioners, HR specialists, workers and applicants dealing with AI solutions coming from the academia and the private/industry sector. The second phase, starting at M20, will be based on quarterly facilitated online discussions to be hosted on the BIAS-Free Helix platform. These asynchronous discussion sessions will be complemented by three joint sessions on web conferencing tools. In this phase, engaged stakeholders will be from the recruitment industry sector, and AI ecosystems involving the EU academia, SME, and industrial actors, along with standardization and AI ethics experts.</p>
<p>Awareness raising events</p>	<p>Awareness raising consists of in-person national workshops and online sessions sharing the results of WP3 technical development and WP4 ethnographic interviews. All these activities will result in having a large, trained community of AI researchers, practitioners, and companies who are aware of the opportunities and pitfalls of AI regarding bias, ensuring that these concerns are integrated in how they carry out their work.</p>
<p>Regulatory acceptability workshop</p>	<p>BIAS will engage directly in conversation with CEN CENELEC to develop a Workshop Agreement together with other stakeholders on the topic of bias for AI in the workplace, based on the IEEE guidance document and British Standard (BS) 8611:2016 "Robots and Robotic Devices. Guide to the ethical design and application of robots and robotic systems." This workshop will be held in Brussels with representatives from CEN CENELEC as well as from the technical developers (NTNU, BFH) and industry partners (DIGI, FARPL).</p>

10.5 Annex 5 – Google Form for BIAS news

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Submit your BIAS news!

Hello everyone! :)

To involve all of you in the communication of the BIAS project and to make sure that all the new contents and results that are being developed within each WP have the due prominence in the BIAS social media and website, LOBA has created this form, which will be shared within the consortium. Through this form, **1 person per organisation** can share which new contents could be published in the communication channels. After a review and curation of these contents, they are organized according to their priority and contemplated in the next monthly plan.

Until the 10th of each month, we kindly ask you to fill in this form with the content that you would like to see published during the next month.

Lead partner: This is the main responsible partner for the event/result/activity to be promoted and the one inserting the information in the form:

Your answer

Other partners contributors (if applicable): Identify other partner/s that have contributed to the event/result/activity:

Your answer

Share your communication:

- Internal events (e.g.: co-creation workshops, capacity building sessions, raising awareness sessions, etc.)
- External events (e.g.: conferences, forums, etc.)
- Results (e.g.: scientific papers, reports, deliverables, etc.)
- News and articles (written by you or by others, but relevant to the project's mission)
- Other

Event/result/activity description and context:Your answer
_____**When to communicate (if there's a date needed):**Your answer
_____**Tags or mentions to be included in the post (if applicable):**Your answer
_____**Upload images (if applicable):**

Write down the link where we can find them.

Your answer

Add any link/URL that should be included in the post:

Your answer

Submit

Page 1 of 1

Clear form

10.6 Annex 6 – Splash Page

BIAS
Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market

Welcome to BIAS What are the project goals? How? For whom? Project Members

AI used in the labour market needs to be **trustworthy** and **socially responsible**.

BIAS
Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market

Welcome to BIAS

A four-year project that will empower the AI and Human Resources Management (HRM) community by addressing algorithmic biases and mitigating them.

Artificial Intelligence is increasingly deployed in the labour market to recruit, train, and engage employees or monitor for infractions. Therefore, the BIAS project will investigate its use in this context. The project will also study how human and societal biases are potentially reproduced in AI-based systems and develop tools to identify and mitigate these biases.

WHAT ARE THE PROJECT GOALS?

Develop the Deblaser, a proof-of-concept for innovative technology based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Case Based Reasoning for an HR recruitment use case. The system will contain two modules: one for bias detection and another for bias mitigation

Gain a richly detailed understanding of bias in recruitment and HRM, which advances the field of worker studies and improves the capacity building activities in the area

Engage in robust stakeholder engagement and co-creation for the development of the Deblaser

Inform future trajectories of NLP and AI research with increased involvement of marginalised people/communities in the design, development, training, and deployment of AI

Empower the AI and HRM community to develop better technology and institute better practices, as well as raise awareness about the importance of addressing algorithmic bias

Make hiring practices less biased and more equal and fair

How?

Through an interdisciplinary research strategy, consisting of

Needs analysis, stakeholder involvement, and co-creation (through National Labs, surveys, interviews and workshops)

AI/NLP research and development

Ethnographic network

Combined with an impact strategy

Awareness raising and capacity building

BIAS modules available to the AI/NLP community

Pathway to a marketable product

Networking and clustering

FOR WHOM?

01 Key Players

Specific Platforms using AI systems to analyse data

New technologies developers

Public and private investors

02 Contact partners

Policy makers at international level

Standardisation organizations

Professional networks and platforms for both businesses and employees

03 Advocates

Individual workers

Educators (secondary and higher education)

Citizen groups and advocacy organizations

Academics, researchers, and think tanks

WHO ARE THE PROJECT MEMBERS?

NTNU

[visit website](#)

UNIVERSITY OF ICELAND

[visit website](#)

LOBA

[visit website](#)

CrowdHelix

[visit website](#)

UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

[visit website](#)

UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN

[visit website](#)

Digitouch

[visit website](#)

farplas

[visit website](#)

UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

[visit website](#)

Website coming soon

But meanwhile, [contact us](#)

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Funded by the European Union

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LOBA

10.7 Annex 7 – Social Media templates

10.8 Annex 8 – Templates Stationary Materials

10.9 Annex 9 – Fundraising round terminology

Type of round	Meaning
Grant	It refers to a grant that a company can receive from a local, national Government, European Commission, incubator, university, or other grant providing agencies.
Angel	It refers to a fund raising round where only angel investor(s) has/have provided investment.
Seed	Typically happens within 3 years of company incorporation with ticket size up to 2-3 M €.
Early VC or Series A, B, C	This corresponds to the initial stages of VC backed investment. Typically termed as Series A, B, C etc., the amount can be up to 20-25 M € typically, and exceptionally more.
Late VC	Investment rounds typically after Series C and 5-8 years of operation and amount raised is more than 20 M €.
Growth Equity	It refers to investment from Private Equity (PE) firms. Companies raise typically more than 20 M €.
Total or majority acquisition	When majority/controlling stake is acquired, or a company is 100% acquired.
Convertibles	It includes convertible notes or convertible loans.

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Consortium

NTNU

UNIVERSITY
OF ICELAND

LOBA[®]

CrowdHelix

SMARTVENICE

Universiteit
Leiden
eLaw

DigiTouch

farplas

Bern University
of Applied Sciences

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